

An Economic Analysis of Bolus-sensor Technology for Precision Dairy Cattle Management

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Abstract

Bolus-sensors are a precision livestock farming tool measuring physiological, behavioural, and production indicators of individual animals to improve herd productivity. Bolus-sensors collect data such as animal activity, rumination, and body temperature. On dairy farms, these data may be used to assess general cattle health, detect oestrus, and monitor presence of disease.

This study focuses on oestrus detection and clinical mastitis (CM) monitoring via bolus-sensors on two dairy farms in northeastern Germany. The two farms use an automatic (AMS) and a conventional milking system (CMS), respectively. A Monte Carlo partial budgeting analysis is performed to quantify the probability of positive net economic outcomes after bolus-sensor adoption. Following previous economic research, the bolus-sensor is assumed to affect milk production and herd growth rates. Annual net economic outcomes are calculated for the two target functions and combined to assess the overall outcome when the bolus-sensor is utilised as a multi-functional tool.

Analysis results show that economic outcomes differ across farm types and functions considered. For CM monitoring, the probability of bolus-sensor adoption leading to increased profits is 58% on AMS farms and 99% on CMS farms. Conversely, the probabilities for oestrus detection on AMS and CMS farms are 80% and 59%, respectively. When the two functions are combined, the likelihood of increased profit is 75% on AMS farms and 93% on CMS farms. Annual economic benefits span from €26,470 to €110,301 on the AMS farm, and from €27,420 to €197,763 on the CMS farm. The mean economic advantage for both target applications is €126,257 year⁻¹ on the AMS farm and €214,670 year⁻¹ on the CMS farm. However, these outcomes are highly variable and more data on the effects of bolus-sensors on herd productivity are required. Additionally, further research is needed to identify potential trade-offs among economic benefits, animal welfare, and other non-economic aspects.

Keywords: partial budgeting, Monte Carlo simulation, mastitis monitoring, oestrus detection, precision livestock farming

1. Introduction

Precision livestock farming (PLF) is a management system relying on continuous, real-time, and automatic collection of data related to individual animal behaviour, health, welfare, production, reproduction, and possibly environmental impact (Mayo *et al.*, 2019; Herlin *et al.*, 2021). PLF technologies are adopted to optimise livestock system efficiency (Mayo *et al.*, 2019). Since the advent of milking robots in the 1990s, sensor technologies capable of measuring physiological, behavioural, and production indicators of individual animals have gained increased attention in PLF (Steenefeld *et al.*, 2015; Herlin *et al.*, 2021). These tools may replace or even enhance human inspection, thus leading to substantial labour savings, while also enabling more intensive livestock management by markedly increasing the amount of collected data (Herlin *et al.*, 2021). Frequent, precise, and systematic data collection may also improve farmers' ability to abide with animal welfare standards, which are increasingly being imposed via regulation globally (Herlin *et al.*, 2021).

Sensors can be categorised as animal- and non-animal-based (Herlin *et al.*, 2021). Animal-based sensors may be fixed to ear tags, worn as collars or leg straps, or administered to the animal in the form of boluses (Herlin *et al.*, 2021). Non-animal-based sensors are usually developed for indoor systems and installed in the animals' vicinity (e.g., heat stress detection cameras) (Herlin *et al.*, 2021). On dairy cattle farms, sensor systems are increasingly being used on a large scale to optimise farmers' decision-making processes (Steenefeld *et al.*, 2015). These sensors may provide information on feed and water intake, oestrus, calving, and presence of disease (Herlin *et al.*, 2021). Certain diseases may even be detected before the manifestation of clinical signs, thus helping reduce milk losses and antimicrobials use (Kim *et al.*, 2019; Herlin *et al.*, 2021). Because most research efforts have concentrated on single-use sensors (Benaissa *et al.*, 2020), this analysis focuses on two target applications in dairy

cattle systems to understand the economic performance of multi-functional sensor technology. The type of sensor studied is an animal-based sensor-bolus placed in the cattle reticulorumen.

The first target application of the selected technology is the monitoring of clinical mastitis (CM). CM has been the first focus of sensor development in the dairy sector (Hogeeven *et al.*, 2010). It usually occurs during lactation, thus severely impairing milk quantity and quality parameters on dairy farms (Kim *et al.*, 2019). Early CM detection may reduce negative economic and animal welfare impacts (Kim *et al.*, 2019). Using temperature data for CM detection is a reliable approach (e.g., Kim *et al.*, 2019). This is especially true when data are gathered by sensor-boluses which, unlike external sensors, have no temperature interference from the surrounding ambient (Kim *et al.*, 2019; Herlin *et al.*, 2021). When compared to other diseases, CM leads to short-lived internal body temperature increases (Kim *et al.*, 2019). Temperature data are usually augmented by other data types (e.g., cattle activity parameters) to improve CM detection accuracy. CM is conventionally monitored via visual inspection of pre-milk (Hogeeven *et al.*, 2010; Kim *et al.*, 2019). This makes it impossible to detect mastitis at the subclinical stage because clinical symptoms must first manifest (Kim *et al.*, 2019). On dairy farms using automatic milking systems (AMS), CM monitoring via visual observation is even more challenging (Hogeeven *et al.*, 2010). Alternative approaches to identifying CM cases include milk colour and homogeneity tests, measurement of milk electrical conductivity (EC), and quantification of L-Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) or somatic cell counts (SCC) in milk (Hogeeven *et al.*, 2010). Of these, EC, LDH and SCC are the most reliable (Hogeeven *et al.*, 2010), but LDH and SCC usually require third-party laboratory tests whose cost hinders farmers' motivation to diligently manage this disease (Boker *et al.*, 2023). Thus, when visual observation of pre-milk is infeasible or impractical (e.g., on AMS farms), EC readings are frequently used to monitor CM and identify milk samples requiring laboratory testing (Steenefeld *et al.*, 2015). Since the EC of milk can also be affected by factors other than CM presence, temperature and other data collected by sensors may further improve the efficiency of EC monitoring systems (Hogeeven *et al.*, 2010).

The second target application of the studied technology is oestrus detection. The reproduction efficiency of cattle significantly affects profitability on dairy farms (Benaissa *et al.*, 2020). The most common approach to oestrus detection is visual observation of animals manifesting sexually receptive behaviours that are associated with reproductive readiness (Mayo *et al.*, 2019; Lodkaew *et al.*, 2023). Because this method is labour-intensive, costly, and prone to errors (Mayo *et al.*, 2019; Lodkaew *et al.*, 2023), sensor technologies are increasingly being used to monitor such behaviours automatically and continuously on dairy farms (Mayo *et al.*, 2019; Benaissa *et al.*, 2020; Lodkaew *et al.*, 2023). If oestrus is not promptly detected, farmers may fail to artificially inseminate cattle at the optimal time before ovulation and must wait for another reproductive cycle (Lodkaew *et al.*, 2023). Breeding failure results in fewer calf births and consequently in lower herd growth rates (Lodkaew *et al.*, 2023). Previous research indicates that economic losses amount to US\$ 360 per missed oestrus (Mayo *et al.*, 2019). Sensor systems have been shown to detect 80-85% of oestrus events, compared to approximately 55% when these are identified via visual methods (Steenefeld *et al.*, 2015). Improving oestrus detection by adopting sensor technologies may reduce calving intervals, which is a known contributor to increased milk production on dairy farms (Steenefeld *et al.*, 2015).

The sensor-bolus selected for the present economic analysis is commercialised by smaXtec Animal Care GmbH (Graz, Austria). The smaXtec® sensor-bolus continuously collects body temperature, rumination, water intake, rumen pH, and activity data (smaXtec, 2024). It is currently commercialised in the US, New Zealand, and several European countries (smaXtec, 2024). Upon sensor-bolus administration and activation, data are wirelessly transmitted to the smaXtec Cloud TruD™ and processed by artificial intelligence (AI) (smaXtec, 2024). Subsequently, the user receives processed data on a mobile phone application as well as recommendations for action (smaXtec, 2024). It is here hypothesised that the multi-purpose smaXtec® sensor-bolus could improve the economic performance of dairy farms. Economic effects of its use for CM monitoring and oestrus detection are assumed to be variations in milk production and herd growth rates. A Monte Carlo (MC) simulation is performed to quantify these effects on two dairy farms located in Germany. The two farms are an AMS farm and a conventional milking system (CMS) farm. Results are generated to answer the three following research questions (RQ): (i) what is the probability that smaXtec® provides a positive economic net outcome compared to conventional CM monitoring approaches? (RQ1); (ii) what is the probability that smaXtec® provides a positive economic net outcome compared to oestrus detection via visual observation? (RQ2); and (iii) what is the probability that smaXtec® provides a positive economic net outcome when simultaneously considering CM monitoring and oestrus detection applications? (RQ3). Interpretation of results is conducted from an agroecological perspective by discussing some implications of sensor-bolus adoption that go beyond economic considerations.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Description of the modelled farms

The two fictitious farms modelled in this study are located in the State of Brandenburg in northeastern Germany. On the AMS farm, conventional CM monitoring and oestrus detection methods are assumed to be EC readings and visual observation of cattle behaviour, respectively. The EC readers are installed on the AMS. AMSs may be sold with an optional SCC sensor (e.g., GEA Group, 2024), but these sensors often rely on California Mastitis Test protocols, which have been questioned for their low specificity rate (e.g., Lam *et al.*, 2009; Kim *et al.*, 2019). Besides, a farm survey of 414 dairy farms conducted by Steeneveld *et al.* (2015) in the Netherlands found that EC sensors were the most widely used sensor types on AMS farms. Thus, this analysis assumes that the AMS is not equipped with SCC sensors and that the farm manager sends milk samples identified via EC readings to a laboratory for diagnosing CM via more reliable tests such as the Porta SCC (Lam *et al.*, 2009). The adoption rates of AMSs are difficult to quantify because equipment retailers do not make their data publicly available (Eastwood and Renwick, 2020). A recent estimate reported that 15% of German dairy farms used AMSs as of 2018 (Eastwood and Renwick, 2020). Thus, a second CMS farm was included in this study because CMSs are still widely used in Germany. On the modelled CMS farm, conventional CM monitoring is conducted via visual observation of pre-milk (Lam *et al.*, 2009; Boker *et al.*, 2023), while conventional oestrus detection follows the same method of the AMS farm. Labour times for conventional CM monitoring and oestrus detection are based on authors' experience. It is assumed that it takes 15 minutes to monitor the EC sensors at each milking event for the entire herd on the AMS farm, and 15 seconds per cow at each milking event to visually assess pre-milk on the CMS farm. Average milkings per day are assumed to be 2.7 and 2.2 on the AMS and CMS farms, respectively. For oestrus detection, visual observation of cattle behaviour requires 50 minutes per day for the entire herd. The farm labour hourly rate is assumed to be € 21.00 per hour (Achilles *et al.*, 2020). The herd size is 227 milking cows, coinciding with the mean herd size in Brandenburg (Tergast *et al.*, 2023).

Both the AMS and CMS farms adopt the smaXtec® bolus-sensor system and move away from conventional CM monitoring and oestrus detection practices. Milk production and herd growth rate variations pre- and post-adoption of the bolus-sensor system are obtained from Steeneveld *et al.* (2015). Milk production is simulated via 10,000 MC iterations using mean, standard deviation, and correlation parameters provided in Steeneveld *et al.* (2015). The assumed milk price is the weighted average price in Germany in 2023 (CLAL, 2024). Herd growth rate increases are 2.50% and 2.20% on the AMS and CMS farms, respectively (Steeneveld *et al.*, 2015). Calf value is € 136.65 head⁻¹ (Saxon State Ministry for Energy, Climate Protection, Environment and Agriculture, 2024). This value is for bull calves, which are assumed to be sold after four weeks following common practice in the study area (Tergast *et al.*, 2023). On the other hand, heifer calves are usually kept on farm as replacement cattle (Tergast *et al.*, 2023). Calf management costs are assumed at € 69.81 per bull calf from birth to sale (Redman, 2023). The latter include direct labour and variable costs such as milk substitute, concentrate, and bedding (Redman, 2023).

2.2. Description of the adopted bolus-sensor system

The smaXtec® bolus-sensor has a size of 105 x 35 mm (**Figure 1**) (smaXtec, 2024). It is administered orally using conventional bolus applicators (smaXtec, 2024). It has a data measurement frequency of 10 minutes and an internal memory capacity of 6 days (smaXtec, 2024). The smaXtec® classic bolus collects the following data types: (i) inner body temperature (accuracy of $\pm 0.01^\circ\text{C}$), (ii) water intake, (iii) rumination, and (iv) animal activity (smaXtec, 2024). The adoption of the smaXtec® system involves three cost components. The upfront cost per sensor-bolus in Germany is € 29.99 (smaXtec, 2024. Pers. Comm.). The sensor-boluses have an average useful life of 5 years (smaXtec, 2024. Pers. Comm.). Subscription costs depend on the herd size, but these are on average € 2.99 per sensor per month (smaXtec, 2024. Pers. Comm.). Subscription costs cover data processing, internet connection, customer support and sensor replacement charges in case of technical failure (smaXtec, 2024. Pers. Comm.). Based on these figures, the per-cow annual cost of the smaXtec® technology is estimated at € 41.88. Additionally, the smaXtec® system requires the installation of a base station costed at € 6,500, including infrastructure, installation labour, and farmer training fees (smaXtec, 2024. Pers. Comm.). The base station is where the data continuously collected by the sensor-boluses are processed. It is equipped with a common subscriber identity module card, an antenna, a bolus applicator and climate sensors collecting ambient temperature, air pressure, and humidity data (smaXtec, 2024. Pers. Comm.). The base station communicates with the smaXtec Cloud TruD™ and provides the user with processed data, alerts, and recommendations for action via a mobile application (smaXtec, 2024. Pers. Comm.). With an assumed useful life of 10 years, base station costs are estimated at € 1007.50 year⁻¹ herd⁻¹. This figure includes annual insurance (assumed at € 65.00 year⁻¹, i.e. 1% of the base station cost) and opportunity cost of capital (€ 292.50 year⁻¹ based on the most recent European Central Bank fixed rate of 4.50%).

Figure 1. The classic smaXtec® bolus-sensor (smaXtec, 2024)

Following personal communication with smaXtec Animal Care GmbH, it is assumed that it requires approximately 15 minutes per day to supervise the mobile application alerts received by the system for the entire herd. For the herd size considered in this study, this is equivalent to 0.40 hours per cow per year for either CM monitoring or oestrus detection. The smaXtec® system exploits AI algorithms to provide farmers with CM case probabilities for individual animals based on body temperature, rumination, and activity data (smaXtec, 2024. Pers. Comm.). CM can be confidently detected after a second alert but, depending on the specific CM pathogen, certain CM cases may be detected at the first alert (e.g., *E. coli* CM) (smaXtec, 2024. Pers. Comm.). This may enable substantial savings in antimicrobial use and laboratory testing even on AMS farms where the EC sensors cannot detect EC changes in milk up to 48 hours after the first smaXtec® system alert (smaXtec, 2024. Pers. Comm.). For oestrus detection, the smaXtec® AI algorithms rely on rumination activity and animal movement patterns (smaXtec, 2024. Pers. Comm.). System alerts are triggered when an animal behaves in a substantially different manner compared to the rest of the group (smaXtec, 2024. Pers. Comm.).

Although sensitivity and specificity percentages of the smaXtec® sensor are not available, this preliminary analysis assumes that this system has a reasonably accurate performance for the two tested functions. Ingestible sensors are an effective tool for CM monitoring, especially when body temperature data are correlated with additional biometric data (Hogeveen *et al.*, 2010; Kim *et al.*, 2019). According to Hogeveen *et al.* (2010), the minimum specificity and sensitivity of a CM detection system should be 80% and 99%, respectively. It is here assumed that the smaXtec® system meets these requirements. Likewise, sensor-supported activity monitoring is regarded as the most successful tool for oestrus detection (Benaissa *et al.*, 2020). Thus, for oestrus detection, the smaXtec® sensor is assumed to at least match the previously reported 80-85% oestrus detection rate (Steenefeld *et al.*, 2015). These assumptions will be revised in future research as more data become available.

2.3. Description of the partial budgeting model

The partial budgeting model used in the present economic analysis relies on the approach by Davies *et al.* (2022). Davies *et al.* (2022) conducted a MC simulation with 10,000 iterations to explore the net economic outcomes of transthoracic ultrasonography testing in subclinical cases of pulmonary adenocarcinoma in live sheep. This methodology is applied to the use of the smaXtec® system for CM monitoring and oestrus detection in dairy cattle over one year to quantify the probability of increased profit after the adoption of smaXtec®. The economic factors considered include a higher milk production and an increased herd growth rate (Steenefeld *et al.*, 2015). The latter is a result of potentially shorter calving intervals. The net economic outcomes for CM monitoring (Scenario 1) and oestrus detection (Scenario 2) are separately calculated and subsequently combined to estimate an overall net outcome when smaXtec® is used as a multi-purpose technology (Scenario 3) (**Table 1**). The relative influence of individual model parameters is explored via sensitivity analyses. The model was developed in Microsoft® Excel® (Microsoft Corporation, 2024).

Table 1. Scenarios tested in the Monte Carlo partial budgeting model

Net economic outcome	AMS farm	CMS farm
Clinical mastitis monitoring	Scenario 1a	Scenario 1b
Oestrus detection	Scenario 2a	Scenario 2b
Overall net economic outcome	Scenario 3a	Scenario 3b

Net economic outcomes in Scenarios 1 and 2 are calculated via **Eq.1**. The individual components of **Eq.1** are estimated using **Eq.2**, **Eq.3**, and **Eq.4** for Scenario 1 and **Eq.5**, **Eq.6**, and **Eq.7** for Scenario 2. Overall net outcomes (i.e., Scenario 3) are calculated via **Eq.8**.

$$\text{Net outcome} = [\text{Effect on revenue (a)}] - [\text{Increased costs (b)}] + [\text{Saved costs (c)}] \quad (1)$$

$$a^{CM} = \Delta\alpha * HS * p \quad (2)$$

where a^{CM} is the effect on revenue of using smaXtec® for CM monitoring (€ year⁻¹); $\Delta\alpha$ is a stochastic variable accounting for the effect on milk production after adoption of the smaXtec® system (l cow⁻¹); HS is the herd size of the modelled farm; and p is the average weighted milk price in Germany in 2023 (€ kg⁻¹).

$$b^{CM} = (\beta_1^{CM} * lab + \gamma_1) * HS + \gamma_2 \quad (3)$$

where b^{CM} is the cost increase incurred after adopting smaXtec® for CM monitoring (€ year⁻¹); β_1^{CM} is the labour time requirement to monitor the CM alerts on the smaXtec® application (h year⁻¹ cow⁻¹); lab is the hourly labour rate in Germany (€ h⁻¹); γ_1 is the yearly adoption cost per cow of the smaXtec® system excluding infrastructure costs (€ year⁻¹ cow⁻¹); γ_2 is the yearly adoption cost per herd for the infrastructure costs of the smaXtec® system (€ year⁻¹ herd⁻¹); and HS is described in **Eq. 2**.

$$c^{CM} = \beta_0^{CM} * lab * mpd * 365 * HS \quad (4)$$

where c^{CM} are the costs saved thanks to the adoption of the smaXtec® system for CM monitoring (€ year⁻¹); β_0^{CM} is the labour time requirement to monitor CM via visual observation of pre-milk (h milking⁻¹); mpd are average milkings per day; and HS and lab are described in **Eq.2** and **Eq.3**, respectively.

$$a^{OD} = (\Delta\alpha * HS * p) + (\Delta HS * HS * cv) \quad (5)$$

where a^{OD} is the effect on revenue of using smaXtec® for oestrus detection (€ year⁻¹); ΔHS is the herd growth rate increase after adoption of smaXtec® (%); cv is bull calf value in Germany as of April 2024 (€ head⁻¹); and $\Delta\alpha$, HS and p are described in **Eq.2**.

$$b^{OD} = (\beta_1^{OD} * lab + \gamma_1) * HS + \gamma_2 + \Delta HS * HS * cmc \quad (6)$$

where b^{OD} is the cost increase incurred after adopting smaXtec® for oestrus detection (€ year⁻¹); β_1^{OD} is the labour time requirement to monitor the oestrus detection alerts on the smaXtec® application (h year⁻¹ cow⁻¹); cmc is the bull calf management cost until its sale (€ head⁻¹); lab , γ_1 , HS , and γ_2 are described in **Eq.3**; and ΔHS is described in **Eq.5**.

$$c^{OD} = \beta_0^{OD} * lab * HS \quad (7)$$

where c^{OD} are the costs saved thanks to the adoption of the smaXtec® system for oestrus detection (€ year⁻¹); β_0^{OD} is the labour time requirement to detect oestrus via visual observation of cattle behaviour (h year⁻¹ cow⁻¹); and HS and lab are described in **Eq.2** and **Eq.3**, respectively.

$$\text{Overall net outcome} = a^{CM} + a^{OD} - b^{CM} - b^{OD} + c^{CM} + c^{OD} - \gamma_1 * HS - \gamma_2 \quad (8)$$

where a^{CM} , b^{CM} , c^{CM} , a^{OD} , b^{OD} and c^{OD} are the outputs of the previous six equations; HS is described in **Eq.2**; and γ_1 , γ_2 are described in **Eq.3**. The latter are subtracted from the overall net outcome to avoid double counting of the smaXtec® system adoption costs.

3. Results

The probability that smaXtec® provides a positive net economic outcome compared to conventional CM monitoring approaches was 58% on the AMS farm and 99% on the CMS farm (RQ1). Annual mean net economic outcomes for Scenarios 1a and 1b are shown in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Mean net economic outcomes of clinical mastitis (CM) monitoring via smaXtec®. Standard deviation values are provided in parentheses.

	AMS farm (Scenario 1a)	CMS farm (Scenario 1b)
Effect on revenue (a^{CM})	€ 33,671 (± € 138,444)	€ 194,234 (± € 86,930)
Increased costs (b^{CM})	€ 12,421 (± € 0)	€ 12,421 (± € 0)
Saved costs (c^{CM})	€ 5,220 (± € 0)	€ 15,950 (± € 0)
Mean net economic outcome	€ 26,470	€ 197,763

The probability that smaXtec® provides a positive net economic outcome compared to oestrus detection via visual observation was 80% on the AMS farm and 59% on the CMS farm (RQ2). Annual mean net economic outcomes for Scenarios 2a and 2b are shown in **Table 3**.

Table 3. Mean net economic outcomes of oestrus detection via smaXtec®. Standard deviation values are provided in parentheses.

	AMS farm (Scenario 2a)	CMS farm (Scenario 2b)
Effect on revenue (a ^{OD})	€ 116,990 (± € 132,843)	€ 34,044 (± € 112,344)
Increased costs (b ^{OD})	€ 13,077 (± € 0)	€ 13,012 (± € 0)
Saved costs (c ^{OD})	€ 6,388 (± € 0)	€ 6,388 (± € 0)
Mean net economic outcome	€ 110,301	€ 27,420

The overall economic outcome of smaXtec® adoption was calculated by combining the mean net economic outcomes shown in **Table 2** and **Table 3**. The probability of overall increased profits was 75% on the AMS farm and 93% on the CMS farm (RQ3). Cumulative distribution functions and descriptive statistics of overall net economic outcomes for the two farms are provided in **Figure 2**. The cumulative distribution function of the CMS farm was found to stochastically dominate its AMS counterpart in the first-degree sense. The expected shortfall at 10% level on the AMS farm was substantially larger than that on the CMS farm indicating that adopting the smaXtec® system was a greater investment risk for the former farm type.

Figure 2. Cumulative distribution functions and descriptive statistics of overall net economic outcomes for the AMS and CMS farms when smaXtec® is used as a multi-purpose technology (Scenarios 3a and 3b)

Finally, sensitivity analyses were conducted to quantify the influence of the input data on the estimated net economic outcome probabilities. Parameter sensitivities were tested between 50% and 150% of the correspondent baseline value with a 25% step. Probability variations of up to 1% were considered negligible and were therefore not reported in this paper. Positive net outcome probabilities were found to be slightly sensitive (-2%) to a 50% milk price reduction on the AMS farm for CM monitoring (Scenario 1a) and on the CMS farm for oestrus detection (Scenario 2b). In the latter scenario, the probability of a positive economic outcome was also sensitive to a 50% smaller herd size (+2%), and a 50% reduction (+2%) or increase (-2%) in the per-cow costs of the smaXtec® system (i.e., the γ_1 parameter).

4. Discussion

The mean net economic outcomes shown in **Table 2** and **Table 3** are always positive on both the AMS and the CMS farms. However, their magnitude depends on the milking system type considered. The AMS farm had a higher probability of obtaining a positive economic outcome when smaXtec® was used for detecting oestrus, whereas the CMS farm was more likely to achieve economic benefits when this technology was used for CM monitoring. Indeed, it is known that farms equipped with different milking systems tend to adopt sensors for distinct target applications (Steenefeld *et al.*, 2015). When the AMS farm used smaXtec® for CM monitoring besides oestrus detection, the probability of achieving a positive economic outcome decreased from 80% to 75% (-5%). Similarly, on the CMS farm, utilising smaXtec® as a multi-functional sensor resulted in a 6% reduction of

positive economic outcome probability from 99% to 93%. Thus, both farms were more likely to benefit from the smaXtec® system when this was used as a single-purpose technology targeting the most economically beneficial function i.e., oestrus detection on the AMS farm and CM monitoring on the CMS farm.

The high standard deviation values in Scenarios 1 and 2 indicate that effects on revenue, and consequently economic outcomes, were extremely variable. This was particularly the case on the AMS farm, where the expected shortfall at 10% level in overall net economic outcomes (Scenario 3a) spanned from € -602,418 to € -114,842. The high variability is also reflected in the remarkably wide range between minimum and maximum overall profits for both farm types (**Figure 2**), though the first-degree stochastic dominance of the CMS curve indicated that smaXtec® adoption was a less risky investment in Scenario 3b. This high variability is due to the uncertain effects of sensor adoption on milk production. In the scientific literature, data on these effects are rarely available or do not possess sufficient detail to correlate productivity parameters with specific sensor types. For example, in the study by Steeneveld *et al.* (2015), the effects on milk production after adopting a CM monitoring sensor were aggregated for colour, EC, SCC, LDH, or other sensors despite distinct approaches achieving substantially different levels of accuracy. More field studies are required to fill this data gap.

To further explore the uncertain effects of sensor adoption on farm economic outcomes, sensitivity tests were performed on all deterministic parameters. Depending on the milking system type and target sensor function, positive net outcome probabilities were found to be only slightly sensitive to milk price, herd size and cost of the smaXtec® bolus-sensors and monthly subscription costs. On the AMS farm, a 50% milk price reduction resulted in a 2% decrease of the positive net outcome probability when monitoring CM (Scenario 1a). A comparable decrease was found on the CMS farm when smaXtec® was used to detect oestrus (Scenario 2b). However, such a milk price has not occurred since June 2016 (CLAL, 2024). The lowest annual average milk price after 2016 was encountered in 2020, corresponding to a 28% reduction in 2023 prices (CLAL, 2024). A 25% milk price reduction reduced the probability of increased profits by 1%. Herd size and per-cow smaXtec® costs affected net economic outcome probabilities in Scenario 2b. A 50% smaller herd size led to an increased probability of positive economic outcomes by 2%. Considering the lack of influence of parameters such as herd growth rate, calf maintenance costs, personnel costs and labour requirements, this was likely due to savings in the per-cow cost of the smaXtec® system. Indeed, γ_1 was ten times the base station cost per cow (i.e., γ_2/HS) with a herd size of 223 and still about five times the base station cost per cow when herd size was 50% smaller. A 50% reduction and increase in personnel costs and labour requirements led to a 2% increase and a 2% decrease in positive net outcome probabilities, respectively. The relatively low influence of the tested parameters seems to corroborate that the milk production effect of sensor adoption is the most important variable.

The cost increases across scenarios mainly resulted from the investment required to adopt the smaXtec® technology. These were always greater than the saved costs except for Scenario 1b. Nevertheless, the initial investment in the smaXtec® system appeared to be economically viable in all scenarios because of positive effects on revenue resulting from higher milk production and/or herd growth rates. The largest cost savings (€ 15,950) were achieved in Scenario 1b. Substituting visual observation of pre-milk for smaXtec® CM monitoring led to a large reduction in labour requirements, which was an important contributor to the high probability of achieving economic benefits after its adoption on the CMS farm. Labour savings are often regarded as a major driver for adoption of sensors and automatic milking systems on conventional dairy farms (Steeneveld *et al.*, 2015; Eastwood and Redwick, 2020). A strong motivation for adopting sensor systems for CM monitoring on AMS farms might be antimicrobial use and laboratory test savings when mastitis is treated at the sub-clinical stage. However, these savings could not be quantified in this analysis in the absence of accurate data.

A lower reliance on antimicrobial use and lower laboratory testing requirements, but also an increased work flexibility and a reduction in repetitive physical work are some of the potential non-economic and more agroecologically based benefits of smaXtec® adoption. Assigning a monetary value to improved working conditions is difficult. However, besides labour cost savings, reduction in drudgery and an improved work-life balance are among the major drivers for farmers' adoption of AMSs (Eastwood and Redwick, 2020) and animal sensors (Steeneveld *et al.*, 2015) across the world. The smaXtec® technology seems to be technically capable of enabling these benefits while maintaining economic feasibility. Besides, continuous, unbiased and reliable data collection from individual animals through sensors may facilitate abiding with animal welfare standards (Stygar *et al.*, 2021). Compliance with such standards is gaining a growing attention from European consumers, who are willing to pay a 31% premium for milk produced on dairy farms proactively managing animal health and welfare (Stygar *et al.*, 2021). Due to this increased attention by consumers, animal welfare standards are increasingly being mandated by regulation.

In Germany, the Animal Welfare Act of 1972 and subsequent amendments requires livestock managers to regularly supervise animal health (Bundesministerium der Justiz, 1972). When animal health is monitored with the aid of technology, the Act imposes the implementation of precautionary measures in case of technical

malfunctions (Bundesministerium der Justiz, 1972). The smaXtec® system has a failure rate of 3% (smaXtec, 2024. Pers. Comm.). When data transmission from a sensor-bolus stops, the system sends an error message to the user via the dedicated mobile application. After a second error message, the user receives an automated email. The farmer has 6 days to replace a faulty sensor without losing animal data, which keep being collected even when they are not wirelessly transmitted to the base station. Other issues may occur if cattle walk too far from the base station, if the base station goes offline, or if the bolus-sensor battery runs out (smaXtec, 2024. Pers. Comm.). In all these cases, alerts will be triggered so that the farm manager may promptly act to solve the issue and implement precautionary measures if needed. However, more studies are required to validate sensor-based welfare assessment, especially on commercial farms (Herlin *et al.*, 2021; Stygar *et al.*, 2021). Animal welfare is a multidimensional concept which is unlikely to be captured by a single technology and potential trade-offs should be taken into consideration (van Erp-van der Kooij and Rutter, 2020). For example, replacing human contact with sensors for monitoring CM and oestrus may lead to increased stress when animals are manually handled for other tasks (Herlin *et al.*, 2021). Stygar *et al.* (2021) investigated into the commercial validation rate of available PLF sensor technologies for animal welfare assessment. They found that only 14% of the 129 identified technologies had been validated, with sensor-boluses representing the least validated category (7%).

5. Conclusions

The present analysis focused on the economic performance of the smaXtec® bolus-sensor system implemented for CM monitoring and oestrus detection on fictitious AMS and CMS dairy farms in Germany. Probabilities of positive net economic outcomes were estimated using a partial budgeting approach and a Monte Carlo simulation of the effect of bolus-sensor adoption on milk production and herd growth rates. The probability of achieving increased profits on the AMS farm for CM monitoring and oestrus detection were 58% and 80%, respectively. On the CMS farm, the probabilities were 99% for CM monitoring and 59% for oestrus detection. When smaXtec® was used as a multi-purpose tool targeting both functions, positive net outcome probabilities were 75% on the AMS farm and 93% on the CMS farm.

Depending on the target application, the mean annual net economic outcomes of smaXtec® adoption ranged from € 26,470 to € 110,301 on the AMS farm, and from € 27,420 to € 197,763 on the CMS farm. When the two target applications were simultaneously considered, the mean overall net economic outcome was € 126,257 year⁻¹ on the AMS farm and € 214,670 year⁻¹ on the CMS farm. The higher profits were mostly due to the increased milk production, higher herd growth rates and labour savings achieved after adopting the studied technology. However, the economic performance of the smaXtec® system was found to be highly variable and consequently these results should be interpreted with care.

Agroecologically based benefits of bolus-sensor adoption on dairy farms may include an increased work flexibility, a reduction in repetitive physical work and an improved compliance with animal welfare standards and regulation. However, these aspects are not well documented in the scientific literature, especially as far as animal welfare is concerned. Further research is required to identify potential economic, social, and environmental trade-offs of sensor-bolus use on dairy farms in Germany and globally.

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